

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

T4.1 - Interview protocol to Identify enablers and barriers to co-design, co-develop and co-implement innovative solutions for climate resilience

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101093921

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Background

The aim of the interviews was to identify how current public policies support co-production processes implementation, but also what changes are needed in the existing instruments to improve policies. A supportive policy framework must enable adaptation practitioners to initiate, engage with relevant participants, implement and facilitate a collaborative process tailored to the local context. This semi-structured interview protocol was used to gather local policymakers experience and perspectives.

The interview protocol is divided in 3 sections and included 15 open-ended questions:

- Section A gathered information about the interviewee position, role and experience with policy-making and co-production processes.
- Section B focused on examples of co-production processes involving citizens locally, the objectives associated with citizen involvement and the ways in which participants have been able to influence these processes.
- Section C was dedicated to their perspectives on the policy frameworks supporting citizen participation in adaptation processes. It first focused on existing policies or instruments and resources allocated to co-production process in terms of funding, human resource, legal framework and institutional support. Then, on policy mechanisms or instruments that are still lacking or could be improved to develop more supportive policy frameworks in the future. Two final questions were posed on ways to make these policies applicable and to promote their implementation, as well as how citizens can support policymakers in enhancing the policy frameworks.

In addition to the interview protocol, interview guidelines, a draft invitation email for policymakers, and a consent form were provided to support partners with conducting the interviews.

Targeted stakeholders

This interview protocol targets municipal and regional policymakers to obtain feedback from the field where the co-production processes for adaptation are being implemented. Possible stakeholders are considered as policymakers, members of public authorities and administrations, and/or actors in charge of or taking active part in local/regional policymaking. Other criteria to select interviewees could be their active participation in climate adaptation co-production processes. We define policymaking as the involvement in any step of the policy cycle from envisioning to design, implementation, evaluation or monitoring (e.g. local/regional adaptation plans, risk management plans or landscape planning).

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Interview design and general considerations

In this section, the interview protocol will be outlined with the different sections which should always include:

- 1- A consent form following legal requirements designed to ensure the confidentiality of the interviews and obtain respondent`s agreement for audio recording, the use of anonymized interview content in publications, and the retention of contact details for future activities of the dedicated project.
- 2- Introduction to the interview, explaining to interviewees the framework under which it will be carried out, the length and structure of the interview.
- 3- Questions
- 4- Enabling future links with respondents

Consent Form Example

Consent form & Privacy policy for AGORA interviews

The EU project AGORA (“we”, “us”) is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy. This Privacy Policy sets out the basis on which your personal data will be processed by us in connection with our communication and dissemination processes. Please read the following document carefully, to understand our views and practices regarding your personal data and how we will handle it. When you fill out this consent form, these Privacy Policy provisions will apply to our processing of your personal data. For further information on how data are processed in AGORA, please consult the project’s Data Privacy Plan.

About the AGORA Project

[AGORA](#) is a project funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) under grant agreement No. 101093921. Agora aims to leverage best practices, innovative approaches, policy instruments and governance mechanisms to meaningfully and effectively engage communities and regions in climate actions, accelerating and upscaling adaptation process for building a climate resilient Europe.

Purpose of the interview

To increase the relevance, acceptability and effectiveness of adaptation initiatives, collaborative processes involving citizens and stakeholders for co-producing these solutions are increasingly developed. The interview aims to gather policymakers' experience, knowledge and perspectives on policy-based support that are available or needed to support adaptation practitioners in implementing such processes, especially linked to citizen engagement. These interviews will be carried out in the four AGORA’s pilot regions (Germany, Sweden, Spain and Italy). The interview will feed the development of a roadmap for transformational change and upscale of citizen engagement, for transferability of effective policy instruments and for ensuring long term legacy.

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Purpose of data processing

If you consent, your personal data may be used for informing you about the progress and results of the Project but also to invite you to other AGORA project activities such as peer-learning workshops linked to policy or governance. The data will be retained for as long as necessary to implement the Project and any related obligations. Storage times may vary depending on the project and its peculiarities.

If you consent, the interview will be recorded to ensure that all information necessary for the purpose of the research is captured. This recording will be used for research purposes only and will not be disclosed to any third party and will be deleted once the necessary data has been extracted.

Categories of data that will be stored

If you consent to the processing of your personal data for the above-mentioned purpose, the categories of personal data that will be collected and stored through the Agora project are:

- Name
- Contact information (e-mail address, position and workplace)

Data sharing

None of these data will be shared publicly, unless you specifically indicate your consent at the end of this statement. Email addresses and names will never be shared publicly. Data can be amended at any time. Data will only be shared internally with the AGORA project core team. You can find a list of all project partners on <https://adaptationagora.eu/consortium/>. The Consortium will process the personal data of subjects according to the present statement and for the purposes declared herein.

Security of Processing and Data Retention

The security and protection of your personal data is very important to the Consortium. Thus, we guarantee maximum confidentiality of the communicated data and employ security measures to maintain the necessary confidentiality. The results of the interviews can be disclosed, both to the Partners and to third parties, in an aggregated or anonymised form and in any case in ways that do not allow the identification of the Data Subject.

Legal basis of processing

We process your data based on your informed consent (Art.6(1)(a) GDPR). You can revoke your consent at any time without giving any reason by contacting info@adaptationagora.eu Any revocation of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Exercise of your rights

In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, you have the following rights:

- Right to request access to their personal data and the rectification or erasure of such data
- Right to restrict processing of your data

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- Right to object to the processing of your data
- Right to data portability, namely right to receive your data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable form so that they can be transferred to another data processor.
- Additionally, you have the right to submit a written complaint to the responsible supervisory body for personal data protection in each country.

For any privacy-related issues and inquiries regarding the processing of personal data, as well as to exercise the rights provided for by the GDPR, you can contact the Partners at the address of the common contact point: info@adaptationagora.eu

Data controller and consent

The data controllers Partner **XXX, located in XXX at INSTITUTE ADRESS,** is responsible for enforcing this data agreement.

Considering all the above information, I _____ (name and surname) confirm my interest in the AGORA project and in taking part in this interview.

Therefore, I consent to the processing of personal data, necessary for the execution of the project activities, as indicated above.

I consent to the recording of the interview and that the information provided will be anonymized and used for research purposes only.

Date

Signature

Interview Introduction

Despite the growing impact of climate change, the adaptation of human populations and activities is lagging. To increase the relevance, acceptability and effectiveness of adaptation initiatives (e.g. adaptation plans, behavioural changes, implementation of technical solutions, solutions based on nature, etc.), collaborative processes involving citizens and stakeholders for co-creating, -implementing and -developing these solutions are increasingly developed. It is in this context that we would like to ask you about your experience, knowledge and perspectives on policy-based support that are available or needed to support adaptation (or any other sector the interviewee is more familiar with) practitioners in implementing such processes, especially linked to citizen engagement.

The interview will be divided into three main parts:

- The first focuses on your position and experience in terms of policymaking;
- The second on current citizen engagement in adaptation processes in your municipality/or region;

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The last one on existing and future policy framework to support adaptation practitioners in citizen engagement.

Section A: Position and influence

Duration: 5min (approx.)

1. In which institution are you working?
2. What is your role within the institution?
3. What is the scale of your action? (Local, regional, national, international)
4. Does your role involve participation in the policy-making process, encompassing any stage from visioning and designing to implementation and monitoring/evaluating? In general, what is your experience in policymaking, at any level?
5. Have you already been involved co-creation/participatory processes and citizen engagement? What role did you have in the process (organiser, participants...)?

Section B: Citizen engagement in adaptation processes

Duration: 15/20mins (approx.)

6. Can you provide us with examples of citizens **actively** participating in *adaptation* processes that you have been involved/know about in your municipality/region? (e.g. citizen juries, climate assemblies, participatory budgeting)? [See Q9 [here](#) for a fuller list]
7. How were citizens able to contribute to/influence the *adaptation* processes that you mentioned in the previous question? (e.g. setting the aims, sharing experiences, creating solutions, taking decisions, implementing interventions)
8. What was the purpose of engaging citizens in these *adaptation* processes?
8bis. Was it related to one of these broad outcomes?
 - Making solutions relevant to the local area
 - Promoting mutual learning
 - Achieving just representation
 - Fostering stronger collaboration
9. Was the process voluntary or mandatory?

Section B: Existing and future policy framework

Duration: 30/40mins (approx.)

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A prior systematic literature review reveals that with a supportive policy framework providing clear guidance, resources and incentives for collaboration, stakeholders and citizens are more likely to engage in co-production activities. Now, we would like to discuss existing policy framework and what progress should be made to incentivize decision-makers and practitioners to implement collaborative adaptation (or other sectors) processes involving citizens.

10. What type of policies or instruments did support citizen participation in *adaptation* processes (e.g. *voluntary or binding mechanisms, nature of the participatory elements, local observatory of citizen participation*)?

11. In existing policies, what resources are allocated to (or available for) *adaptation* practitioners to involve citizens in climate adaptation? (e.g. *funding, human resources, legal framework, institutional support*)

12. What policy mechanisms or instruments are still lacking or could be improved to develop a more supportive policy framework in the future? What is still needed?

12bis. Especially in terms of:

- Legal frameworks (e.g. binding processes)?
- Sustainable funding (e.g. incentives)?
- Allocation of trained human resources (e.g. boundary organisations, civil servant training)?
- Political/institutional support (e.g. political leadership)?
- Bonus: Shaping a more efficient institutions' organisation/functioning (e.g. breaking silos)?
- Bonus: Dealing with power imbalance (e.g. vulnerable people involvement)?

13. Are there lessons that can be learnt from other sectors/topics (e.g. mitigation, hazard regulation, digitalization...)?

Last questions:

14. Despite existing policy frameworks, a strong implementation gap remains. What can be done to make these policies applicable and encourage their implementation?

15. How can citizens support policymakers to improve the policy framework?

Thank you and Way forward

If you would like to be kept informed and follow the activities of the AGORA project, you can subscribe to the newsletter. If you want to be involved in future activities, such as peer-learning workshops linked to policy or governance (held in spring 2025), please specify it and we will keep your contacts to invite you to future events.

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